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Review Article

A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural Fibre

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Abstract

Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing can be established by developing completely eco-friendly natural dyes and natural finishing agent which can be applied on cotton textiles (Oeko-Tech Products) by adopting a newer technique of simultaneous Mordanting-Dyeing-Finishing in a single step to reduce energy cost, process time, processing costs and effluent load as well as to develop the single step processes and also completely eco-friendly products of cotton textiles using selective natural dyes and natural finishing agents using bio mordants and bio finishing agents obtained from an extract of natural resources at reduced cost and energy. There is huge scope of commercialization of such Oeko-Tech (Eco-Friendly) products of natural dyed and finished cotton textile products for domestic and export market. Different selective natural dyes like teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood, skin of onion, arjuna bark etc., bio-mordanting agent like bio-enzyme, harda, lemon as natural mordanting agents, extracted soyabean seed as natural chemical modification as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent where all dyed and finished fabric can be scientifically tested by SEM, FTIR, DSC, HPLC, GCMS, TLC, CHNS, X-ray diffraction pattern etc.

Introduction

Worldwide growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products is generating more and more customer's interests on natural fibres based textile as well as on natural dyes and natural finishing, particularly for the Export market. Considering this corner, textile sector has the highest scope to apply this research work for attracting the value-added customer. But, till today there is a huge lack of research and development of natural dyeing and finishing based textile product. There are ample scopes of doing scientific research on the application of natural dyes on cotton and other textiles aimed at obtaining newer shade with acceptable colour fastness behaviour and uniform and reproducible colour yield through appropriate techniques. Simultaneous natural dyeing and natural finishing: a new technique will thus serve process steps like energy and total process cost. Reducing process cost will minimize total cost of the product in the export market, it will be highly beneficial

to sustain in a competitive market if the expected research output can be applied successfully in Government and non-government textile mill at home and abroad.

Cotton is still a natural fibre of agro-origin that is used most in the world. About 46% of all fibre produced in the world is cotton. Even today cotton is the backbone of the world's textile trade. The cotton fibre presents many exceptional features like great flexibility, cohesive property, very small thickness, but high strength and wear resistance. Owing to these properties it is possible to process cotton fibres into yarns with greater diversity; from thick yarn for manufacturing coarse and different upholstery/furnishing as well as denim type apparel fabrics to very fine yarns for manufacturing thin and refined fabrics such as Batiste, Marquisette, Muslin, etc. Cotton fibre is widely used for making all types of apparels as well as all types of furnishing fabrics. In textile applications this biodegradable, environment-friendly and renewable fibre has some

distinct advantages such as moderate dry and wet tensile strength, appreciable moisture regains, agreeable feel, moderate extensibility, varied dye ability and appreciable UV-light stability. However, the major disadvantages of cotton lie in its dimensional instability as revealed by wash shrinkage, poor wrinkle recovery and ready susceptibility to microbial degradation.

Natural dyes are considered to be eco-friendly as these are obtained from renewable resources as compared to synthetic dyes which are derived from non-renewable petroleum resources. These are biodegradable and the residual vegetal matter left after extraction of dyes can be easily composted and used as fertilizer. They produce soft colours soothing to the eye which is in harmony with nature which is gradually gaining popularity due to its non-toxicity and eco-friendly character against possible unsafe ecotoxicity criteria of synthetic dyes. Most of the studies available for dyeing with natural dyes relates to cotton textiles and such studies on cotton are still insufficient to establish. Hence, there are ample scope of undertaking an integrated study in this area for cotton and chemically modified cotton to study its surface appearance, durability and dyeing of cotton and chemically modified cotton with natural dyes.

Literature Review

Growing consciousness for eco-friendly textile products has caused more interest on cotton fibre based natural dyeing and finishing. Productions of synthetic dyes are dependent on the petrochemical source and some of the synthetic dyes contain toxic/carcinogenic amines and are not eco-friendly. Contrary to this, most of the natural dyes as well as natural finish with few exceptions are based on vegetable/ animal origin and are renewable, biodegradable, energy-efficient and eco-friendly[1,2]. The most important issue now is origin and classification of some natural dyes applicable for different fibres are available in the literature [3-5]. Gupta, et al. [6] have documented some of the traditional processes of application of some natural dyes. Kawahito, et al. [7] have compared the dyeing of cellulosic fabric with natural indigo and synthetic indigo. Radhakrishnan[8] as well as Ajita, et al.[9] have reported the effect of different mordants on selective natural dyes. Grierson, et al. [10] has studied colour fastness characteristics of some natural dyes. Lee, et al. [11] have studied the colour fastness properties of some natural dyes by applying UV-absorbers. Effect of chemical structure on light fastness property of some natural dyes has been reported by Gupta, et al. [12]. Oda, et al. [13] has studied the effect of phenyl ester functional group on photofading of carthamin on cellulose acetate. Most of the studies are sporadic and insufficient in developing scientific knowledge base on the subject. Therefore, very less study on simultaneous natural dyeing and finishing, dyeing process variables and characterisation etc. Hence, an integrated scientific study for selective natural dye-fibre system, for selective natural dyes applied on cotton and other textiles is felt necessary, for establishing the process optimization in naturally dyed textiles. [14, 15 16, 17] Natural dyes, natural mordanting agent, natural finishing

agent and standard industrialized process of natural dyeing and finishing were experimented in earlier research on natural coloration.

Application of Different Biomordanting with Biomordanting Agents

Effects of different degrees of biomordanting like bioenzyme, harda and lemon as natural mordanting agents and natural chemical modification extracted from soyabean seed on cotton fabric for altering its textile related properties and dye ability with selective natural dyes (say a teak leaf, turmeric, Jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) can be investigated. Effect of such biomodifications on colour parameters after dyeing of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified cotton and its colour fastness properties to light, washing, perspiration and rubbing can be studied. The photo fading behaviour of cotton and chemically and biochemically modified and dyed cotton materials after those modifications and pre-treatments and subsequent dyeing can be studied and an attempt can be taken to improve the same to a much better level of customer acceptability. Effects of different degree of chemical modifications on colour yield for the selective natural dyes can be studied. Cotton Textile materials dyed with natural dyes can be post-treated/finished with suitable natural agents for studying the effect of these after treatments on the improvement of colour yield, brightness and colour fastness behaviour of the dyed material. To improve the colour fastness properties for the selective natural dyes some pre or post-treatment with cationic or metallic complex compound or UV absorbers/suitable modifiers can be studied.

Process Development

The fabrics can be pre-treated by the eco-friendly enzyme-based chemical pre-treatment processes for preparing it for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. After that different natural dyes (say teak leaf, turmeric, jackfruit wood, sappan wood etc.) as well as natural finishing agent like coconut oil as UV absorber, neem and guava leaf as antimicrobial agent can be applied on cotton fabric for trailing and experimentations on application of dyes and finishing agent on cotton and optimization of dyeing process variables for improved colour development and improvement of colour fastness, all analytical testing. Effects of variations of dyeing process variables on colour yield and dyeing kinetics for application of selective natural dyes on cotton and chemically modified cotton substrate can be investigated to understand the dyeing isotherm, rate of dyeing and other thermodynamic parameters for such dyeing. This will help to understand the dyeing behaviours of different natural dyes applied on cotton to get an idea of formulating better colour yield having specific standardized dyeing recipe for combined/compound shades by use of binary or ternary mixture of these natural dyes. For use of combination of natural dyes for generating compound shades, a study on the compatibility of such binary and a ternary mixture of dyes can be also studied, to understand and find a compatible combination of such dyes for cotton

and chemically treated and modified cotton fabrics.

Process of Textile Properties and Dyeability Analysis

Changes in structural features for different degrees of chemical modifications (enzymatic hydrolysis, oxidation on cotton substrate) can be investigated with the help of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Sulphur (CHNS) analyzer and X-ray diffraction pattern etc. for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behaviour and dyeability in terms of changes in structural features of chemically modified cotton substrate along with changes in surface characteristics and durability etc.

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